

FracRisk

Reporting form for deliverables

Deliverable Number:	D3.1
Work package number:	3
Deliverable title	Update of FEP database (Version 2)
Type	Report
Dissemination Level	R
Lead participant	UGOE
Contributing scientists and other personnel	A. Tatomir, C. McDermott, K. Edlmann, J. Bensabat, H. Wiener, Y. Goren
Schedules delivery date from DOW	1/12/2015
Actual / forecast delivery data	1/12/2015
Comments (optional)	This is a dynamic document and will be updated as the project progresses. This is state of the art as of 1.12.2015, and forms the technical description to the ranking of the FEP's, D4.1.
Deliverable summary text:	<p>A database of features, events and processes as well as hazards, impacts and controls for assisting in the identification of critical combinations of subsurface geology, operational practice of hydraulic fracturing and associated hazard and risk assessment for the natural and human environment is presented. The aim of this work is to provide a realistic comprehensive list of possible environmental impacts of shale (unconventional) gas exploration and exploitation. This work provides the basis for further hazard and risk evaluation through numerical modelling and the development of monitoring and mitigation techniques designed to efficiently identify and significantly reduce any environmental impacts. In addition the work forms the backdrop to the development of EU legislative recommendations.</p>
Submitted	1.12.2015
Reviewed	Click here to enter text.
Final submission	Click here to enter text.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 636811

FracRisk:

Furthering the Knowledge Base for
Reducing the Environmental Footprint of
Shale Gas Development

Update of FEP database

(Version 2)

November 2015

Contents

I.	General Considerations	8
A.	Definitions.....	8
B.	Objectives.....	8
II.	List of Features.....	11
A.	Features of the Natural System	11
1.	Hydrogeology.....	11
1.1.	Hydrocarbon bearing formation (Source)	11
1.1.1.	Type of the hydrocarbon bearing formation	11
1.1.2.	Geometry of the hydrocarbon bearing formation.....	11
1.1.3.	Rock / Petrophysical properties of the hydrocarbon bearing formation	12
1.1.4.	Stress and Mechanical properties	13
1.1.5.	Heterogeneity of the hydrocarbon bearing formation	13
1.1.6.	Fractures and faults within the hydrocarbon bearing formation	14
1.1.7.	Undetected features within the hydrocarbon bearing formation.....	14
1.1.8.	Vertical geothermal gradient of the hydrocarbon bearing formation	14
1.1.9.	Formation pressure of the hydrocarbon bearing formation	14
1.2.	Fluids	14
1.2.1.	Hydrocarbons.....	14
1.2.2.	Natural formation water	14
1.2.3.	Production fluids.....	14
1.2.4.	Pore fluid composition within the fracking reservoir	15
1.2.5.	Reservoir fluids	15
1.2.6.	Other fluids	15
1.3.	Overburden	15
1.3.1.	Geometry of the overburden.....	15
1.3.2.	Rock / Petrophysical properties of the overburden	15
1.3.3.	Free gas pocket within the overburden	17
1.3.4.	Additional seals within the overburden	17
1.3.5.	Unconformities within the overburden	17
1.3.6.	Heterogeneity within the overburden	17
1.3.7.	Fractures and faults within the overburden	17
1.3.8.	Undetected features within the overburden.....	17

1.3.9.	Vertical geothermal gradient of the overburden	17
1.3.10.	Formation “overburden” pressure.....	17
1.3.11.	Overburden pressure.....	17
1.4.	Underburden	18
1.4.1.	Geometry of the underburden	18
1.4.2.	Rock / Petrophysical properties of the underburden.....	18
1.4.3.	Unconformities within the underburden	19
1.4.4.	Heterogeneity within the underburden	19
1.4.5.	Fractures and faults within the underburden.....	19
1.4.6.	Undetected features within the underburden	19
1.4.7.	Vertical geothermal gradient within the underburden.....	20
1.4.8.	Formation “underburden” pressure.....	20
2.	Near surface environment (Receptors).....	21
2.1.	Terrestrial environment.....	21
2.1.1.	Geographical location	21
2.1.2.	Soils and sediments.....	21
2.1.3.	Near-surface aquifers and surface water bodies.....	21
2.1.4.	Terrestrial flora and fauna	21
2.1.5.	Terrestrial ecological systems.....	21
2.1.6.	Buildings.....	21
2.2.	Marine environment.....	22
2.2.1.	Local oceanography.....	22
2.2.2.	Marine sediments.....	22
2.2.3.	Marine Stratification and Mixing	22
2.2.4.	Marine flora and fauna.....	22
2.2.5.	Marine ecological systems	22
2.3.	Human Environment.....	23
2.3.1.	Human characteristics.....	23
2.3.2.	Diet and food processing	23
2.3.3.	Lifestyles.....	23
2.3.4.	Land and water use	24
2.3.5.	Community characteristics	24
2.4.	Atmosphere and meteorology	24

B.	Unconventional Hydrocarbon Extraction	25
1.	Hydro-fracturing fluid.....	25
1.1.	Hydraulic injection fluid properties.....	25
1.2.	Physical properties of injection fluid.....	25
1.2.1.	Injection fluid additives	25
1.2.2.	Hydro-fracturing fluids interactions	25
2.	Site development	25
2.1.	Logistics above ground	25
2.2.	Baseline monitoring	25
3.	Site operation	25
3.1.	Drilling and completion.....	25
3.1.1.	Horizontal wells	26
3.1.2.	Formation damage	26
3.1.3.	Well lining and completion	26
3.1.4.	Workover	26
3.1.5.	Monitoring wells.....	26
3.1.6.	Well records.....	26
3.1.7.	Well orientation.....	27
3.1.8.	Well engineering.....	27
4.	Site decommissioning	27
4.1.	Closure and sealing of boreholes	27
4.2.	Abandoned wells	27
III.	List of Events	27
1.	Operational Events	28
1.1.	Multiple well drilling from same platform	28
1.2.	Initial drilling to given below water table (Open Hole)	28
1.2.1.	Casing emplacement	28
1.2.2.	Cementation with wiper plug	28
1.2.3.	Drilling through wiper plug and casing shoe.....	28
1.2.4.	Additional cementation.....	28
1.3.	Logging Borehole.....	28
1.4.	Drilling horizontal borehole.....	28
1.4.1.	Casing horizontal borehole	28

1.4.2.	Cementation	28
1.4.3.	Perforation	28
1.5.	Hydraulic fracturing	28
1.5.1.	Out of zone / beyond pumping.....	28
1.6.	Plugging & drilling out of plugs.....	28
1.7.	Flow back.....	28
1.7.1.	Production.....	28
1.8.	Abandonment.....	28
1.9.	Seal failure	28
2.	Natural events	28
2.1.	Earthquakes.....	28
2.2.	Large scale erosion.....	28
2.3.	Hydrological and hydrogeological response to geological changes	28
2.4.	Cap rock failure	28
2.5.	Unexpected large scale scenario	28
3.	Accidents and unplanned events.....	28
3.1.	Surface chemical spills	29
3.2.	Overpressuring	29
3.3.	Poor site characterization.....	29
3.4.	Incorrect chemical mix released into fracking fluid	29
3.5.	Cementation poorly undertaken (spaces left).....	29
3.6.	Well lining too limited, open hole left.....	29
3.7.	Inappropriate management of drill cuttings and spent drilling muds.	29
3.8.	Unlikely significant event.....	29
IV.	List of Processes:.....	30
1.	Thermal effects on the borehole.....	30
1.1.	Thermal effects on borehole and seal integrity.	30
1.2.	Thermal effects on the injection point	30
2.	Hydraulics / Fluid Pressure Dominated	30
2.1.	Fluid pressure exceeds rock fracking pressures generating new fractures	30
2.2.	Fluid exceeds fault sealing pressures.....	30
2.3.	Fluid pressure exceeds stability of part of the plant construction.	30
2.4.	Displacement of surrounding formation fluids	30

2.5.	Buoyancy-driven flow	30
2.6.	Advection and co-migration of other gas	30
2.7.	Formation of Gas hydrates	31
2.8.	Water mediated transport.....	31
2.8.1.	Advection	31
2.8.2.	Dispersion	31
2.8.3.	Diffusion	31
2.9.	Hydraulic and production fluids and the associated contaminants release processes.....	31
3.	Chemical.....	32
3.1	Corrosive mixture attacks plant	32
3.2	Corrosive mixture attacks geology	32
3.3	Sorption and desorption	32
3.4	Mineral dissolution	32
3.5	Heavy metal release.....	32
4.	Mechanical.....	32
4.1	Soil and rock deformation around boreholes.....	32
4.1.1	Subsidence of ground related to gas extraction	32
4.2	Propagation of fractures beyond the target zone.....	32
4.3	Fluid exceeds fault sealing pressures.....	32
4.4	Fault valving.....	32
4.5	Generation of excavation disturbed zone around well.....	33
4.6	Micro-cracking in the casing cements.....	33
V.	HAZARDS//RISKS related to subsurface processes	34
A.	Loss of fracturing fluids.	34
B.	Disturbance of in situ substances, leading to release of e.g. contaminants to the subsurface	34
C.	Leakage from the borehole both near surface and deep.....	34
D.	NORM encountered.	34
E.	Well closure and abandonment.....	34
F.	Uncontrolled release of gas and fluid from well bore at surface during drilling operations (blow out)	34
VI.	Possible Impacts	34
A.	Impacts on humans	34

1.1.	Health effects of hydro-fracking, production fluids and associated contaminants	34
1.2.	Pollution caused by substance released during the exploration process is significant enough to cause a breach of environmental standards.....	34
1.3.	Toxicity of contaminants.....	34
1.4.	Impacts from physical disruption	35
1.5.	Impacts from ecological modification.....	35
1.6.	Water acquisition	35
B.	Impacts on flora and fauna	35
2.1	Effect of hydro-fracking, production fluids and associated contaminants on animals	35
2.2	Effect of hydro-fracturing fluids on plants and algae.....	35
2.3	Ecotoxicology of contaminants	35
2.4	Ecological effects.....	35
2.5	Modification of microbiological systems	35
C.	Impacts on the physical environment	35
3.1	Contamination of groundwater.....	35
3.2	Impacts on soils and sediments.....	36
3.3	Management of flow back fluids leads to surface spills	36
3.4	Release to the atmosphere	36
3.5	Impacts on exploitation of natural resources.....	36
3.6	Release to the marine environment	36
3.7	Modified hydrology and hydrogeology.....	36
3.8	Modified geochemistry.....	36
3.9	Modified seismicity	36
3.10	Modified surface topography	36
3.11	Sinkhole formation	36
3.12	Impacts on oceans.....	36
3.13	Subsidence or uplift.....	37
VII.	Controls & mitigations	37
A.	Schedule and planning	37
B.	Pre-closure administrative control	37
C.	Pre-closure monitoring of storage.....	37
D.	Post-fracking closure administrative control	37

E. Post-fracking monitoring.....	37
F. Records and markers.....	37
G. Reversibility.....	37
H. Remedial actions.....	37

I. General Considerations

A. Definitions

- A Feature is a static attribute of a system (e.g., reservoir porosity).
- An Event is a change in the system or its environment (e.g., naturally occurring earthquake).
-

A process is a physical phenomena resulting from the combination of Thermal, Hydraulic, Mechanical, Chemical or Biological (THMCB) effects

B. Objectives

We present a database for assisting in the identification of critical combinations of subsurface geology, operational practice of hydraulic fracturing and associated hazard and risk assessment for the natural and human environment. The aim of this work is to provide a realistic comprehensive list of possible environmental impacts of shale (unconventional) gas exploration and exploitation. This work provides the basis for further hazard and risk evaluation through numerical modelling and the development of monitoring and mitigation techniques designed to efficiently identify and significantly reduce any environmental impacts. In addition the work forms the backdrop to the development of EU legislative recommendations.

Features, Events and Processes (FEP) refers to the identification and selection of the relevant factors for hydraulic fracturing safety: characterization of the main geological features, definition of key events and understanding of main processes occurring during the exploration and exploitation of shale gas.

The critical combinations F-E-P involved in shale gas development will be assembled into a set of focused scenarios (Figure 1) e.g.: 1. Source, fracking processes; 2. Source, fluid injection, fluid migration and micro-seismics; 3. Source characterization, produced fluid and remaining fluid; 4. Pathway: leaking fault zone, abandoned boreholes, target: aquifers, short term; 5. Pathway: leaking fault zone, target: aquifers, long term; 6. Pathway: diffuse vertical migration target: aquifers, long term

Figure 1 Focused scenarios for evaluation of critical combinations of FEP's

The highest ranked FEPs for each focused scenario will be depicted in a bowtie diagram.

A bowtie diagram is a pictorial representation of the links between the potential causes, preventative and mitigative controls and consequences of a major accident.

The bowtie consists of the following elements:

- Hazard: Anything inherent to the business that has the potential to cause harm.
 - Several FEP's belong to one HAZARD. At the end of this document, there is a list of such events coming from the literature.
- Threat: A direct, sufficient and independent possible cause that can release the hazard by producing the top event leading to a consequence.
- Undesirable Event: The moment in which the hazard is released; the first event in a chain of negative events leading to unwanted consequences.
- Consequence: Accident event resulting from the release of a hazard that results directly in loss or damage.

This is illustrated in Figure 2.

Figure 2 Example of main parts of a Bow Tie diagram.

II. List of Features

A. Features of the Natural System

1. Hydrogeology

This category describes natural hydraulic and geologic features (hydrogeological features) of the environment/geosphere relevant to the hydraulic fracturing process. The subsurface is considered in four main compartments, these are the hydrocarbon bearing formation (reservoir), the overburden, underburden and the natural fluids prior to the hydraulic fracturing (Figure 3).

Figure 3: Compartmentalization of the subsurface

1.1. Hydrocarbon bearing formation (Source)

1.1.1. Type of the hydrocarbon bearing formation

The generic hydrocarbon bearing formation type provides a high-level indication of the geological characteristics. It describes the extent and type of historical exploitation of any geological resources, e.g. shale gas, tight gas, coalbed methane reservoir.

1.1.2. Geometry of the hydrocarbon bearing formation

The Geometry of the hydraulic fractured reservoir is a feature including its dimensions (vertical and horizontal), the spatial distribution, depth and the topography of the top. The understanding of formation geometry helps to determine the amount of hydrocarbons and to highlight possible leakage points.

1.1.2.1 Thickness

The thickness is a geological property that expresses its vertical dimensions of the hydrocarbon bearing formation. Determination of the thickness is important for the estimation of the amount of hydrocarbons and planning of the exploitation. For the vertical dimensions several classifications are commonly used in reservoir engineering: gross thickness – the thickness of

the stratigraphically defined interval, including reservoir beds, non-productive interbedded intervals; net pay thickness: the thickness of oil/gas bearing interval.

1.1.3. Rock / Petrophysical properties of the hydrocarbon bearing formation

The petrophysical properties of the hydrocarbon bearing formation rock indicate the physical and chemical rock properties and their interaction with fluids (i.e., lithology, porosity, water saturation, permeability, density).

The petrophysical properties are essential for understanding and predicting the effectiveness and distribution of the hydraulic fractures. They determine how hydraulic fracturing fluids will migrate in the geosphere.

1.1.3.1 Lithology

The lithology indicates the composition or type of rock (e.g. shale, mudstone, claystone). Usually, the rock types are classified in three major categories sedimentary, igneous, and metamorphic. The physical, chemical, and mineralogical properties of the reservoir rocks affect fluid flow and transport in the hydrocarbon bearing formation and the surrounding non reservoir rocks, the rock strength, and elastic properties (such as compressibility, shear strength, Poisson's ratio etc.).

Whether the reservoir rock organic matter is algal, sapropellic or humic will influence the H:C ratio, the O:C ratio and the weight of the hydrocarbons and ultimately determine if the reservoir rock contains oil prone or gas prone hydrocarbons.

1.1.3.2 Diagenesis

Diagenesis defines the physical and chemical changes occurring during the conversion of sediment to sedimentary rock (over geological time). For instance, the lithification process describes the compaction of the rocks by burial and the chemical cementation occurring when minerals come in contact with pore fluids. The lithification is one diagenetic process which changes the physical and chemical characteristics of the reservoir rock. For example, porosity usually decreases during lithification reducing the potential recoverable resources.

1.1.3.3 Pore architecture

The pore architecture determines the porosity and permeability of the rock, which are key features when considering the mobility of fluids and gases within the rock and the fracking density and distribution.

Pore size and pore throat distributions are important classification methods for the porous media.

1.1.3.4 Mineralogy

Mineralogy indicates the minerals and fluid inclusions (from the diagenetic processes) that make up the rock. The mineralogical composition of the rock is an important classification procedure of the reservoirs.

1.1.3.5 Kerogen type

Kerogen is a mixture of organic chemical compounds that make up a portion of the sedimentary rocks. Kerogen type also influences the amount of CO₂ within the source rock

which will have an impact on the recoverable reserves and degree of contaminants in the production stream and any migrating fluids.

1.1.3.6 Thermal maturation of source rock

The temperature the source rock has reached will determine if it has undergone diagenesis, catagenesis or metagenesis and will influence the H:C ratio of the trapped hydrocarbons.

1.1.3.7 Porosity

Porosity is a measure of the void space of the rock. One can distinguish between effective porosity (porosity which is relevant to fluid flow) or total porosity (including void spaces which do not contribute to flow).

1.1.3.8 Intrinsic permeability

Intrinsic permeability is a measure of the ability of a porous media to allow fluids to pass through it.

1.1.3.9 Relative permeability

Relative permeability of a fluid phase (in a multiphase system) is a dimensionless measure of the effective permeability of that phase.

1.1.3.10 Entry pressure

In a multiphase system (e.g., methane – water) the entry pressure is considered the capillary pressure required to displace the wetting phase from the largest occurring pore.

1.1.3.11 Residual saturation

In a multiphase system the residual saturation of a fluid phase represents the parts of fluid which are entrapped and cannot be displaced.

1.1.3.12 Hysteresis

Hysteresis in a multiphase porous media system is describing the non-reversible behaviour of the displacement processes (e.g., imbibition, drainage).

1.1.4. Stress and Mechanical properties

The initial stress state and mechanical properties are a baseline from which the whole hydraulic fracturing strategy will be decided. Mechanical changes of the reservoir resulting from hydrofracturing (such as generation of fractures, reactivation of fractures/faults, changes of bulk elastic properties and effective reservoir) could lead to subsidence/uplift (at surface), induced seismicity, changes in migration pathways, even burst/leakage of the seal. Examples of other relevant processes include borehole lining collapse and rock volume changes, which lead to cracking.

Near the well, fracture orientation is dictated by complex near wellbore stresses, as the fracture develops away from the well it aligns itself collinear with the maximum stress and normal to the minimum stresses.

1.1.5. Heterogeneity of the hydrocarbon bearing formation

Heterogeneities can result in directional variations in petrophysical parameters (e.g., permeability), which affects the mobility of fluids and gases in the rock during fracking.

1.1.6. Fractures and faults within the hydrocarbon bearing formation

Existing faults and fractures can act as migration pathways for hydro-fracking fluids and effect the ability to hydraulically fracture the formation. They can also provide information about how the rocks will fracture and the stress state.

1.1.6.1 Porosity of the fracture

1.1.6.2 Intrinsic permeability of the fracture

1.1.6.3 Relative Permeability of the fractures

1.1.6.4 Fracture geometry

Naturally existing fracture systems are characterized by parameters like width, orientation, length, density.

1.1.7. Undetected features within the hydrocarbon bearing formation

Undetected features could significantly affect the performance of a fracking system, in particular local porosity heterogeneities.

1.1.8. Vertical geothermal gradient of the hydrocarbon bearing formation

Geothermal gradients may influence the mechanical response of the rocks to hydraulic fracturing.

1.1.9. Formation pressure of the hydrocarbon bearing formation

Formation pressure is the static pressure of the fluids in the porous media reservoir. It will influence the mechanical response of the rocks to hydraulic fracturing.

1.2. Fluids

Detailed description of the fluids in the natural system is essential prior to begin of hydraulic fracturing. The flow, transport and interaction behaviours of water and other fluids in the system are affected by the fluid composition.

1.2.1. Hydrocarbons

Hydrocarbons are organic compounds consisting entirely of hydrogen and carbon (e.g., methane). If hydrocarbons are present, such as oil and/or gas, they can be mobilized during the hydraulic fracturing process.

1.2.2. Natural formation water

Natural formation water flow pathways (directions, velocities) in the geosphere are important for understanding the possible migration pathways of the frack-fluids and excess water. This depends on factors including: hydraulic heads, permeability and porosity distribution, the existence of fracture networks, connection between aquifers, position of the recharge and discharge areas.

1.2.3. Production fluids

The produced hydrocarbons may have a range of impurities within the stream that could impact on the production facilities or create an environmental impact if they were to leak.

These include CO₂ which is an organic matter maturation by-product and could be up to 20% of the production gas.

1.2.4. Pore fluid composition within the fracking reservoir

The composition of the released pore fluids are relevant as the hydrocarbons can be various weights of oil, gas or a mix of both. There is also likely to be other contaminants and additional gasses such as CO₂.

1.2.5. Reservoir fluids

The fluid properties and geochemistry of the geosphere will contribute towards determining how any migrating injection fluids or hydrocarbon production fluids will behave in the geosphere

1.2.6. Other fluids

In addition to CO₂ there are likely to be additional gases naturally present in the pore fluids which could accompany the production fluids. These could include H₂S which is highly toxic and therefore potentially harmful.

1.3. Overburden

The overburden defines the geologic unit above the hydrocarbon bearing formation. During the hydraulic fracturing operations fracking fluids can leak in the overburden. Therefore, the overburden and low permeability cap rocks play a key role in preventing any hydro fracking fluid leakage from migrating to the surface.

Similarly to the hydrocarbon bearing formation the overburden geologic formation is characterized by thickness, type, geometry, petrophysical properties, stress and mechanical properties, etc.

1.3.1. Geometry of the overburden

The Geometry of the overburden formation includes its dimensions (vertical and horizontal), the spatial distribution, depth and the topography of the top.

1.3.1.1 Thickness

The thickness is a geological property that expresses its vertical dimensions of the overburden formation. Fracture extent may extend out of the hydrocarbon bearing formation into the overburden formation increasing the likelihood of contamination.

1.3.2. Rock / Petrophysical properties of the overburden

The petrophysical properties of the overburden formation rock indicate the physical and chemical rock properties and their interaction with fluids (i.e., lithology, porosity, water saturation, permeability, density).

The petrophysical properties are essential for understanding and predicting the effectiveness and distribution of the hydraulic fractures. They determine how hydraulic fracturing fluids will migrate in the geosphere.

1.3.2.1 Lithology

The lithology indicates the composition or type of rock (e.g. shale, mudstone, claystone). Usually, the rock types are classified in three major categories sedimentary, igneous, and

metamorphic. The physical, chemical, and mineralogical properties of the reservoir rocks affect fluid flow and transport in the hydrocarbon bearing formation and the surrounding non reservoir rocks, the rock strength, and elastic properties (such as compressibility, shear strength, Poisson's ratio etc.).

1.3.2.2 Diagenesis

Diagenesis defines the physical and chemical changes occurring during the conversion of sediment to sedimentary rock (over geological time). For instance, the lithification process describes the compaction of the rocks by burial and the chemical cementation occurring when minerals come in contact with pore fluids. The lithification is one diagenetic process which changes the physical and chemical characteristics of the reservoir rock. For example, porosity usually decreases during lithification.

1.3.2.3 Pore architecture

The pore architecture determines the porosity and permeability of the rock, which are key features when considering the mobility of fluids and gases within the rock and the fracking density and distribution.

1.3.2.4 Mineralogy

Mineralogy indicates the minerals and fluid inclusions (from the diagenetic processes) that make up the rock. The mineralogical composition of the rock is an import classification procedure of the reservoirs.

1.3.2.5 Porosity

Porosity is a measure of the void space of the rock. One can distinguish between effective porosity (porosity which is relevant to fluid flow) or total porosity (including void spaces which do not contribute to flow).

1.3.2.6 Intrinsic permeability

Intrinsic permeability is a measure of the ability of a porous media to allow fluids to pass through it.

1.3.2.7 Relative permeability

Relative permeability of a fluid phase (in a multiphase system) is a dimensionless measure of the effective permeability of that phase.

1.3.2.8 Entry pressure

In a multiphase system (e.g., methane – water) the entry pressure is considered the capillary pressure required to displace the wetting phase from the largest occurring pore.

1.3.2.9 Residual saturation

In a multiphase system the residual saturation of a fluid phase represents the parts of fluid which are entrapped and cannot be displaced.

1.3.2.10 Hysteresis

Hysteresis in a multiphase porous media system is describing the non-reversible behaviour of the displacement processes (e.g., imbibition, drainage).

1.3.3. Free gas pocket within the overburden

Small gas pockets of free gas may exist above the low permeable hydrocarbon bearing formation within the overburden.

1.3.4. Additional seals within the overburden

Features with the potential to retard or prevent any hydro fracking fluid leakage migration in the geosphere are important considerations when determining the performance of a hydraulic fracturing project.

1.3.5. Unconformities within the overburden

Unconformities can act both as potential seals or lateral migration pathways for fluids.

1.3.6. Heterogeneity within the overburden

Heterogeneities can result in directional variations in permeability, which affects the mobility of fluids and gases in the rock during fracking.

1.3.7. Fractures and faults within the overburden

Existing faults and fractures can act as migration pathways for hydro-fracking fluids and effect the ability to hydraulically fracture the formation. They can also provide information about how the rocks will fracture and the stress state.

1.3.7.1 Porosity of the fracture

1.3.7.2 Intrinsic permeability of the fracture

1.3.7.3 Relative Permeability of the fractures

1.3.7.4 Fracture geometry

Naturally existing fracture systems are characterized by parameters like width, orientation, length, density.

1.3.8. Undetected features within the overburden

Undetected features could significantly affect the performance of a fracking system, in particular local porosity heterogeneities.

1.3.9. Vertical geothermal gradient of the overburden

Geothermal gradients may influence the mechanical response of the rocks to hydraulic fracturing.

1.3.10. Formation “overburden” pressure

Formation “overburden” pressure is the static pressure of the fluids in the porous media “overburden”, located above the reservoir. It will influence the mechanical response of the rocks to hydraulic fracturing.

1.3.11. Overburden pressure

The overburden pressure, also called the lithostatic pressure, is the pressure or stress imposed on a layer of soil or rock by the weight of overlying material.

1.4. Underburden

The underburden defines the geologic unit below the hydrocarbon bearing formation. During the hydraulic fracturing operations fracking fluids can leak into the underburden.

Similarly to the hydrocarbon bearing formation the underburden geologic formation is characterized by thickness, type, geometry, petrophysical properties, stress and mechanical properties, etc.

1.4.1. Geometry of the underburden

The Geometry of the underburden formation includes its dimensions (vertical and horizontal), the spatial distribution, depth and the topography of the top.

1.4.1.1 Thickness

The underburden thickness is a geological property that expresses the vertical dimensions of the underburden formation. Fracture extent may extend out of the hydrocarbon bearing formation into the underburden formation.

1.4.2. Rock / Petrophysical properties of the underburden

The petrophysical properties of the underburden formation rock indicate the physical and chemical rock properties and their interaction with fluids (i.e., lithology, porosity, water saturation, permeability, density).

The petrophysical properties are essential for understanding and predicting the effectiveness and distribution of the hydraulic fractures. They determine how hydraulic fracturing fluids will migrate in the geosphere.

1.4.2.1 Lithology

The lithology indicates the composition or type of rock (e.g. shale, mudstone, claystone). Usually, the rock types are classified in three major categories sedimentary, igneous, and metamorphic. The physical, chemical, and mineralogical properties of the reservoir rocks affect fluid flow and transport in the hydrocarbon bearing formation and the surrounding non reservoir rocks, the rock strength, and elastic properties (such as compressibility, shear strength, Poisson's ratio etc.).

1.4.2.2 Diagenesis

Diagenesis defines the physical and chemical changes occurring during the conversion of sediment to sedimentary rock (over geological time). For instance, the lithification process describes the compaction of the rocks by burial and the chemical cementation occurring when minerals come in contact with pore fluids. The lithification is one diagenetic process which changes the physical and chemical characteristics of the reservoir rock. For example, porosity usually decreases during lithification.

1.4.2.3 Pore architecture

The pore architecture determines the porosity and permeability of the rock, which are key features when considering the mobility of fluids and gases within the rock and the fracking density and distribution.

1.4.2.4 Mineralogy

Mineralogy indicates the minerals and fluid inclusions (from the diagenetic processes) that make up the rock. The mineralogical composition of the rock is an important classification procedure of the reservoirs.

1.4.2.5 Porosity

Porosity is a measure of the void space of the rock. One can distinguish between effective porosity (porosity which is relevant to fluid flow) or total porosity (including void spaces which do not contribute to flow).

1.4.2.6 Intrinsic permeability

Intrinsic permeability is a measure of the ability of a porous media to allow fluids to pass through it.

1.4.2.7 Relative permeability

Relative permeability of a fluid phase (in a multiphase system) is a dimensionless measure of the effective permeability of that phase.

1.4.2.8 Entry pressure

In a multiphase system (e.g., methane – water) the entry pressure is considered the capillary pressure required to displace the wetting phase from the largest occurring pore.

1.4.2.9 Residual saturation

In a multiphase system the residual saturation of a fluid phase represents the parts of fluid which are entrapped and cannot be displaced.

1.4.2.10 Hysteresis

Hysteresis in a multiphase porous media system is describing the non-reversible behaviour of the displacement processes (e.g., imbibition, drainage).

1.4.3. Unconformities within the underburden

Unconformities can act both as potential seals or lateral migration pathways for fluids.

1.4.4. Heterogeneity within the underburden

Heterogeneities can result in directional variations in permeability, which affects the mobility of fluids and gases in the rock during fracking.

1.4.5. Fractures and faults within the underburden

Existing faults and fractures can act as migration pathways for hydro-fracking fluids and effect the ability to hydraulically fracture the formation. They can also provide information about how the rocks will fracture and the stress state.

1.4.6. Undetected features within the underburden

Undetected features could significantly affect the performance of a fracking system, in particular local porosity heterogeneities.

1.4.7. Vertical geothermal gradient within the underburden

Geothermal gradients may influence the mechanical response of the rocks to hydraulic fracturing.

1.4.8. Formation “underburden” pressure

Formation “underburden” pressure is the static pressure of the fluids in the porous media “overburden”, located above the reservoir. It will influence the mechanical response of the rocks to hydraulic fracturing.

2. Near surface environment (Receptors)

This category of FEPs is concerned with factors that can become important if hydraulic fracturing fluids or gas leaks in the accessible environment. The environment can be terrestrial, marine and the human behaviour in that environment. Therefore, the FEPs category is divided into three classes: Terrestrial Environment, Marine Environment; and Human Behaviour.

2.1. Terrestrial environment

This class of FEPs is concerned with factors that can be important if hydraulic fracturing fluids or gas leaks into the accessible terrestrial environment.

2.1.1. Geographical location

Proximity to natural hazards will increase their importance in being considered in the assessment. Proximity to human populations places more emphasis on the significance of near-surface releases.

2.1.2. Soils and sediments

The characteristics of soils and sediments will strongly influence the behaviour of hydro-fracking and production fluids within them. In particular, these characteristics will largely determine the ability of the hydro-fracking and production fluids to interact with the soil / sediment ecosystem and is therefore an important factor when considering exposure of local environmental receptors, such as flora and fauna.

2.1.3. Near-surface aquifers and surface water bodies

Aquifers may yield significant amounts of water to wells or surface springs and may thus be a flow path for hydro-fracking, production and contaminant fluids to the surface environment. Streams, rivers and lakes often act as boundaries of hydrogeological systems. They may represent a significant source of dilution for hydro-fracking, production and contaminant fluids entering these systems..

2.1.4. Terrestrial flora and fauna

Flora and fauna may be affected by concentrations of hydro-fracking, production and contaminant fluids in the near-surface environment and may be indicators of hydro-fracking, production and contaminant fluids leakage. Flora and fauna may also become stressed as a result of increased contaminant concentrations, causing an increased susceptibility to climate change, pollution, etc.

2.1.5. Terrestrial ecological systems

Hydro-fracking, production and / or contaminant fluid leakage may stress ecological systems, which could result in higher susceptibility to other stresses, such as drought, pollution etc.

2.1.6. Buildings

The structure or materials used in building construction can be significant factors for determining potential exposure pathways to hydro-fracking, production and / or contaminant fluids. For example, accumulation of methane in buildings and basements may cause explosions (at concentrations above 4,4% methane), or may lead to adverse health effects due to elevated concentrations.

2.2. Marine environment

Marine environment class of FEPs is concerned with factors that can be important if hydraulic fracturing fluids return to the accessible marine environment.

2.2.1. Local oceanography

Features and processes related to the characteristics of seas and oceans and their evolution. This includes the topography and morphology of the seabed, thermal stratification and salinity gradients, hydrodynamic mixing, and marine currents. Other features may include water column depth, temperature stratification, and salinity. Ocean biogeochemistry (the interactions of biology, chemistry and geology in the ocean), in particular the cycling of materials and nutrients through the different parts of the system, is also included.

The local oceanographic features and processes determine the potential for dilution or accumulation of hydro-fracking, production and / or contaminant fluids in the marine environment.

2.2.2. Marine sediments

Features and processes associated with sediments in the present marine environment. This includes both the physical and chemical characteristics of the sediments, along with sedimentation and resuspension processes.

Marine bed sediment characteristics will influence the ecology of the marine environment. They will also influence relevant processes to consider should hydro-fracking, production and / or contaminant fluids migrate to the marine environment.

2.2.3. Marine Stratification and Mixing

Stratification in marine systems can increase the potential impacts of hydraulic and production fluids and the associated contaminants, especially H₂S and CO₂, on benthic marine flora and fauna by enabling higher CO₂ concentrations to develop over a wider area of the seabed than in the absence of stratification.

2.2.4. Marine flora and fauna

Features and processes related to the characteristics of marine flora and fauna, and their evolution. These flora and fauna include plants, animals, fungi, algae and microbes.

Flora and fauna may be affected by concentrations of hydro-fracking, production and / or contaminant fluids in the marine environment and may be indicators of leakage. Descriptions of the marine flora and fauna therefore provide a baseline against which assessments can be made.

2.2.5. Marine ecological systems

Features and processes related to interactions between populations of algae, animals, microbes and their evolution.

The algal, animal and microbial populations occupying the marine environment are an intrinsic component of its ecology. Their behaviour and population dynamics are regulated by the wide range of processes that define the ecological system.

The ecology of the marine environment determines the types of organisms present and their inter-dependencies. These can influence the types of impact of interest (e.g. nutrient fertilisation) and can provide a mechanism for monitoring any hydro-fracking, production and / or contaminant fluid leakage.

2.3. Human Environment

This FEPs class includes factors that can be important if fracturing fluids or gas leaks into the human environment.

Human behaviour can affect the nature and magnitude of potential impacts to human beings.

2.3.1. Human characteristics

Features and processes related to characteristics, e.g. physiology, metabolism, of individual humans. This FEP includes considerations of variability of physiology and metabolism in individual humans due to age, health, and other features.

Physiology refers to body and organ form and function. Metabolism refers to the chemical and biochemical reactions which occur within an organism, or part of an organism, in connection with the production and use of energy.

Children and infants, although similar to adults, often have characteristic differences, e.g. metabolism and respiratory rates, which may lead to different characteristics of exposure to methane or contaminants.

Human physiology and metabolism can determine the effect of exposure to hydro-fracking, production and / or contaminant fluids.

2.3.2. Diet and food processing

Features related to intake of food and water by individual humans and the compositions and origin of intake. This includes considerations of how diets, of individual humans, may vary with age and other variations (ingestion of soil by infants, for example).

This FEP also includes processes related to the treatment of foodstuffs and water between origin and consumption. For example, once a crop is harvested it may be subject to a variety of storage, processing and preparation activities prior to human or livestock consumption. Water sources may be treated prior to human or livestock consumption, e.g. chemical treatment and/or filtration.

The human diet provides a potentially important exposure pathway to contaminants released into the food chain as a result of leakage of hydro-fracking, production and / or contaminant fluids. Food preparation processes may change the distribution and content of hydro-fracking, production and / or contaminant fluids in the product.

2.3.3. Lifestyles

Human habits will determine the exposure pathways of interest in an assessment. Smoking, ploughing, fishing, and swimming are examples of behaviour that might give rise to particular modes of exposure to hydro-fracking, production and / or contaminant fluids mobilised as a result of hydro-fracking.

2.3.4. Land and water use

FEPs related to land and water use by humans in the near-surface environment and the resulting implications for methane leakage and contaminant transport and exposure pathways. This includes consideration of: - the use of natural or semi-natural tracts of land and water such as forest, brush, rivers, lakes and the sea; - rural and agricultural land and water use (including freshwater and marine fisheries); - urban and industrial land and water use related to developments, including transport, and their effects on hydrology; and - leisure and other uses of environment.

These FEPs can influence the potential transport and exposure pathways for hydro-fracking, production and / or contaminant fluids as well as the potential evolution of the system during the timescales of interest. Particular considerations are relevant for each type of land use addressed, for example: a) special foodstuffs and resources may be gathered from natural land and water which may lead to significant modes of exposure to hydro-fracking, production and / or contaminant fluids; b) an important set of processes are those related to agricultural practices, their effects on land form, hydrology and natural ecology, and also their impact in determining contaminant uptake through food chains and other exposure paths; c) human populations are concentrated in urban areas in modern societies. Significant areas of land may be devoted to industrial activities. Water resources may be diverted over considerable distances to serve urban and/or industrial requirements; d) human populations currently use freshwater resources for agriculture, drinking, etc., but saline water should also be considered as future generations may desalinate and use it for similar purposes; and e) significant areas of land, water, and coastal areas may be devoted to leisure activities. e.g. water bodies for recreational uses, mountains/wilderness areas for hiking and camping activities.

2.3.5. Community characteristics

Features related to characteristics, behaviour and lifestyle of groups of humans that might be considered as target groups in an assessment.

Relevant characteristics might be the size of a group and degree of self-sufficiency in food stuffs/diet. Associated with this is a consideration of the amount of resources required to meet the needs of the community.

This FEP involves a consideration of aggregated human behaviour in order to consider their dependency on and interactions with their environment. It therefore provides input to a consideration of potential human interference with the hydro-fracking system as well as input to considering potential exposure pathways.

2.4. Atmosphere and meteorology

Meteorological characteristics influence the near-surface hydrological regime with its subsequent consequences for hydro-fracking, production and contaminant fluid migration; for example soil moisture levels affect ingress of gas. Atmospheric pressure changes will drive gaseous exchange between the atmosphere and soil gas; this process is termed 'atmospheric pumping'. This process will affect release of hydrocarbons such as methane and contaminants such as CO₂ from soils, and hence CO₂ and methane concentrations in soil gas. The variability

in meteorological characteristics should be considered by any assessment of the consequences of methane emissions from the earth's solid surface or surface water bodies.

B. Unconventional Hydrocarbon Extraction

1. Hydro-fracturing fluid

A typical shale gas well currently requires 10 fracking operations, each of which uses 1,600m³ water, 32 tonnes of sand proppant and 5 tonnes of chemicals.

1.1. Hydraulic injection fluid properties

The fracturing fluid is typically comprised of 99 percent water and sand, with less than 1 percent special-purpose additives. These additives are needed to enable the water-sand mixture to transport the sand deep into the fracture and then change its properties to allow the water to be removed while the sand remains, holding the fracture open.

1.2. Physical properties of injection fluid

Pumps are injecting at high pressure fracturing fluids consisting of water, sand ('proppant') and chemicals to create fractures. After fracturing, fracturing fluid flows back to the surface ('flowback water') containing saline water with dissolved minerals. Fracturing fluid and formation water returns to the surface of the lifetime of the well as it continues to produce shale gas. Although, definitions vary, flowback water and produced water collectively constitute "wastewaters" (EPA, 2011). (Royal Academy of Engineering, 2012).

1.2.1. Injection fluid additives

Common additives include guar gum to make the fluid more gel like to improve effective delivery, nitrogen gas, enzymes or oxidisers to thin the consistency of the guar gum and further chemicals which may be toxic.

1.2.2. Hydro-fracturing fluids interactions

A range of physical and chemical reactions can be important and understanding these interactions is essential for the assessment of potential impacts.

2. Site development

The site development features refer to the features of site during and after its development, e.g. baseline monitoring, logistics above the ground.

2.1. Logistics above ground

Include features which involve any type of logistics necessary for the site development, or for the unconventional hydrocarbon extraction operations.

2.2. Baseline monitoring

Refers to features installed on site for the baseline monitoring of the operations.

3. Site operation

3.1. Drilling and completion

Features relevant to the operation of boreholes drilled within the system domain.

3.1.1. Horizontal wells

Drilling a vertical well to near formation and then drilling horizontally into the shale gas formation significantly reduces the surface footprint while giving access to much more shale gas reservoir than a vertical well. Horizontal wells can be 5km + long for typical formation depths of 2000m tvd.

3.1.2. Formation damage

Formation damage results from exposure to drilling fluids, or mechanical fracturing. The formation damage has influence on the flow and transport parameters (e.g., porosity, permeability).

Formation damage can make information from affected boreholes non-representative of the true characteristics of the un-damaged formations. Damaged regions themselves may result in fracturing out with the planned hydraulic fracs.

3.1.3. Well lining and completion

At the time of drilling, boreholes are lined with a metal casing. Cement is pumped downhole inside the casing string, and it is pushed upward under and outside the casing lower end, between the casing and the rock wall.

Borehole lining and completion results will contribute to determining the performance of the hydraulic fracturing and mitigating any potential leakage pathways.

3.1.4. Workover

The process of performing major maintenance or remedial treatments on a borehole often associated with the re-use of existing boreholes. Workover techniques include flushing of the formation and the removal and replacement of the borehole lining.

Well workovers will result in modified borehole properties that may need consideration within an assessment.

3.1.5. Monitoring wells

Monitoring wells are in certain situations installed to monitor the physical conditions (pressure, temperature, etc.) of the reservoir and the area affected by hydro-fracturing operations.

3.1.6. Well records

The drilling of boreholes for site investigation and/or resource exploitation results in large number of documents. Typical well records include location coordinates, depth, electric logs, mud logs, drilling parameter logs, composite log, testing reports (if applicable), coring report (if applicable), and a final report. Physical records from cutting samples, cores and fluid samples are also documented.

Well records provide a key source of baseline information regarding the reservoir. They provide information concerning the nature of the rocks drilled by the well and their petrophysical characteristics. Additionally, records from wells drilled over a period of time can give a picture of how the system is evolving either naturally, or as a result of the exploitation of geological resources

3.1.7. Well orientation

Relative orientation of the well controls fracture – if the well runs perpendicular to the minimum stress, fractures will develop along the well, if the well runs parallel to the minimum stress the fractures will develop transversely.

3.1.8. Well engineering

Using horizontal wells to reduce environmental footprint providing access to more of the natural gas resources from few surface wells. The well is engineered to ensure the casing and cement program protects fresh water and that the well can reach the intended target reservoir. It will be reinforced with multiple layers of protective steel casing and cement to stabilise the well and protect groundwater and aquifers. Casing is pressure tested after cementing to ensure integrity.

4. Site decommissioning

4.1. Closure and sealing of boreholes

Correct cementing and abandonment operations are essential to achieve restoration of pristine sealing within the reservoir formation.

4.2. Abandoned wells

Old substandard plugged wells could provide a potential leakage route to the surface or into subsurface aquifers.

III. List of Events

An event is defined as a change in the system or its environment. The events can be operational, naturally occurring or as combinations of the two.

1. Operational Events
 - 1.1. Multiple well drilling from same platform
 - 1.2. Initial drilling to given below water table (Open Hole)
 - 1.2.1. Casing emplacement
 - 1.2.2. Cementation with wiper plug
 - 1.2.3. Drilling through wiper plug and casing shoe
 - 1.2.4. Additional cementation
 - 1.3. Logging Borehole
 - 1.4. Drilling horizontal borehole
 - 1.4.1. Casing horizontal borehole
 - 1.4.2. Cementation
 - 1.4.3. Perforation
 - 1.5. Hydraulic fracturing
 - 1.5.1. Out of zone / beyond pumping
 - 1.6. Plugging & drilling out of plugs
 - 1.7. Flow back
 - 1.7.1. Production
 - 1.8. Abandonment
 - 1.9. Seal failure

Seal failure may provide preferential short circuits of pressure and fluids to the surface.

2. Natural events
 - 2.1. Earthquakes

Seismic events may result in changes in the stress state, fracture network and hydro-mechanical properties of rocks.

- 2.2. Large scale erosion

Has the potential to modify the geological or hydrogeological environment. Erosional and depositional processes will influence the way in which the surface environment has evolved and will evolve over the time-scale of interest.

- 2.3. Hydrological and hydrogeological response to geological changes

Flow of groundwater within and surrounding a hydro-fracking site may influence fracking fluid migration, Physical changes to the rock units caused by geological changes may also create or destroy potential pathways for fracking fluid migration.

- 2.4. Cap rock failure
 - 2.5. Unexpected large scale scenario

A site-specific worst case scenario, caused by a natural event. For example, a tsunami wave hitting a pod.

3. Accidents and unplanned events

This category refers to accidents and unplanned events during and after the hydraulic fracturing operations.

3.1. Surface chemical spills

Hydro fracking chemicals leaking from a chemical tank or from a truck following a transport accident. There are around 30 different chemicals that are used in hydraulic fracturing and these can include: Ethylene glycol, Butyldiglycol, Cholinchloride, guar, Carbohydrate derivative and Ethylene glycol monohexyl ether.

3.2. Overpressuring

Accidental or deliberate overpressuring event can affect the integrity of the sealing formation, or of the well. This can further lead to a release of fluids and contaminants into the shallow aquifers.

3.3. Poor site characterization

An insufficient characterization of the geological formations (lack of or incomplete well records) must be considered as it determines the efficiency and safety of the hydraulic fracturing processes. For instance an undetected fault region may allow the fracking-fluid leakage and remain undetected for long time.

3.4. Incorrect chemical mix released into fracking fluid

Accidentally or deliberately releasing an incorrect chemical mix can

3.5. Cementation poorly undertaken (spaces left)

3.6. Well lining too limited, open hole left

Casing must be cemented deeper than the deepest fresh groundwater, this may not always be easily identified. In some cases after the fresh groundwater has been isolated no further cementing is used until a certain height above the hydrocarbon bearing formation is reached. This could leave an uncemented section creating a preferential flow path between layers of the underburden, and lead to methane migration from organic rich layers above the intended hydrocarbon bearing formation.

3.7. Inappropriate management of drill cuttings and spent drilling muds.

Drilling mud is pumped into the borehole to cool the drill bit and act as a means for the resulting cutting debris to leave the well. Inappropriate management of this waste will enable uncontrolled contact between the drilling mud, cuttings and surface environment, particularly surface water and near surface ground water.

3.8. Unlikely significant event

A site-specific worst-case scenario, caused by an anthropic intervention.

IV. List of Processes:

A process is a physical phenomena resulting from the combination of Thermal, Hydraulic, Mechanical, Chemical or Biological (THMCB) effects.

1. Thermal effects on the borehole

1.1. Thermal effects on borehole and seal integrity.

Thermal stress may cause failure of the cement rock seal through cracking.

1.2. Thermal effects on the injection point

Temperature of the injected fluid could result in geological modification of the region around the point of injection due to thermal gradients.

2. Hydraulics / Fluid Pressure Dominated

2.1. Fluid pressure exceeds rock fracking pressures generating new fractures

2.2. Fluid exceeds fault sealing pressures

Large transient releases of migrating injection or production fluids may occur during fault valving episodes.

2.3. Fluid pressure exceeds stability of part of the plant construction.

2.4. Displacement of surrounding formation fluids

Interfacial tension and capillary pressure determine the location of any leaking free phase methane (or other reservoir fluids) within the pore spaces of the formations surrounding the hydrocarbon bearing formation. Consideration needs to be given to the possibility that formation fluids that are displaced by leaking methane may impact upon sensitive domains (i.e. regions within which there are potentially impacted receptors such as organisms).

2.5. Buoyancy-driven flow

Different relative densities of fluids in a geological system will result in buoyancy-driven flows as less dense fluids will have a tendency to flow upwards and more dense fluids will tend to flow downwards. If there is a release of methane, density driven flow will be upwards towards the surface. Density-driven flow of methane released at the ground surface in terrestrial environments may result in impacts to surface/near-surface ecosystems if the concentrations reach sufficiently high levels. Similarly, density-driven methane emitted at sea bed or lakebed may cause impacts to sea/lakebed ecosystems if the concentrations reach sufficiently high levels.

2.6. Advection and co-migration of other gas

Surface seepages of Hydraulic and production fluids and its associated contaminants may contain significant amounts of other gases due to co-migration, such as hydrogen sulphide (H₂S). H₂S is highly toxic and therefore potentially harmful to the biosphere. Even in low concentrations it is deleterious to long-term health (human/animal), in addition to being extremely unpleasant.

The rate and direction of advection is affected by the physical properties of the rock, such as porosity and permeability and the fracture network.

2.7. Formation of Gas hydrates

Gas hydrates are 'ice-like' solids that form at low temperatures and high pressures. If hydraulic fracturing occurs below deep water or permafrost then rising production fluids might hit the hydrate stability zone, approximately less than 15°C and greater than 50 bar (~500 m + depth).

2.8. Water mediated transport

Processes related to the transport of hydro-fracturing fluids, hydrocarbons and the associated contaminants, in formation water /groundwater and surface water. These include advection, dispersion and molecular diffusion. Impacts on sensitive domains (i.e. regions within which there are potentially impacted receptors such as organisms) may arise if such water leaves the hydraulically fractured complex. The patterns of migration and the fluxes of the water will influence the magnitudes of the impacts and their spatial distribution. At a secondary level, dispersion within surface water environments (both freshwater and marine) will influence environmental concentrations of hydraulic and production fluids and the associated contaminants and consequently the potential for any associated impacts.

2.8.1. Advection

Advection is the process by which contaminants, such as methane and hydro-fracturing contaminants are transported by bulk movement of the water in which they are dissolved. Advective water movement can occur along connected porous regions, such as fractures and faults.

2.8.2. Dispersion

Dispersion is the collective name for the consequences of a number of processes that cause 'spreading-out' of contaminants in all directions dissolved in water, superimposed on the bulk movement predicted by a simple advection model. It results in a spatially distributed contaminant plume. Spreading of the solute plume can occur in the direction of advection, in which case it is known as longitudinal dispersion, or it can occur perpendicular to the direction of advection, in which case it is known as transverse dispersion.

2.8.3. Diffusion

Diffusion is the process whereby chemical species move under the influence of a chemical potential gradient (typically a concentration gradient). Diffusion can occur in any direction, and is not related to the direction of flow within the system.

2.9. Hydraulic and production fluids and the associated contaminants release processes

Processes by which the production fluids and the associated contaminants are lost from a hydraulically fractured system. They determine the performance of that system. The area over which hydraulic and production fluids and the associated contaminants is lost, as well as the flux, will influence the area and volume of potentially impacted sensitive domains (i.e. regions within which there are potentially impacted receptors such as organisms) and the

nature/severity of the impacts. Natural gas seepages from hydrothermal vents provide an example of seepages in the marine environment.

3. Chemical

3.1 Corrosive mixture attacks plant

Fracking fluids or flow back fluids may corrode well and plant equipment.

3.2 Corrosive mixture attacks geology

Fracking fluids or flow back fluids corrode geology, e.g. acidified waters attack carbonates.

3.3 Sorption and desorption

The sorption and desorption processes of hydro-fracturing fluid components and of the hydrocarbons on geological materials (e.g., shale, overburden rock).

3.4 Mineral dissolution

The dissolution of minerals due to the addition and migration of hydro-fracturing and/or reservoir fluids.

3.5 Heavy metal release

Within rock formations heavy metals may occur within solid mineral phases and / or could be sorbed onto mineral surfaces. Hydraulic fracturing has the potential to release heavy metals, which may then migrate to water resources with potential impacts of concern.

4. Mechanical

4.1 Soil and rock deformation around boreholes

This process results in changing properties of the soil around borehole casings after abandonment. It may decrease the degree of sealing and therefore the potential for the region immediately around the borehole to act as a migration pathway for hydro-fracking fluids and other associated contaminants.

4.1.1 Subsidence of ground related to gas extraction

4.2 Propagation of fractures beyond the target zone

4.3 Fluid exceeds fault sealing pressures

Large transient releases of migrating injection or production fluids may occur during fault valving episodes.

4.4 Fault valving

Large transient releases of migrating injection or production fluids may occur during fault valving episodes. The patterns of these releases will be controlled by the properties of the particular fault that shows valving behaviour, including its size, geometry, the nature of its intersection with the fluid accumulation, and the mechanical properties of the rocks that it

cuts. If fault valving allows the fluids to leave the hydrofractured complex (i.e. to leak), the nature and spatial extent of impacts upon sensitive domains (i.e. regions within which there are potentially impacted receptors such as organisms) will depend upon the pattern of advection and the flux.

4.5 Generation of excavation disturbed zone around well

4.6 Micro-cracking in the casing cements

During plug drilling micro-cracking in the casing cements may be initiated.

When creating a risk register, it is sometimes easier to work Top-Down – starting with the known hazards of the operations and the possible impacts of it and then analyse what are the combinations of features and events that may lead to these hazards occurring.

For this purpose, a list of expected hazards (section V) and a list of outcomes (section VI) related to hydraulic fracturing were prepared, based on reports by the UK Environmental Agency¹ and Cuadrilla Planning Application².

V. HAZARDS//RISKS related to subsurface processes

- A. Loss of fracturing fluids.
- B. Disturbance of in situ substances, leading to release of e.g. contaminants to the subsurface
- C. Leakage from the borehole both near surface and deep.
- D. NORM encountered.
- E. Well closure and abandonment
- F. Uncontrolled release of gas and fluid from well bore at surface during drilling operations (blow out)

VI. Possible Impacts

Impacts are any endpoint that could be of interest in an assessment of performance and safety. The classes of impact considered are:

- 1) Impacts on Humans,
- 2) Impacts on Flora and Fauna,
- 3) Impacts on the Physical Environment

A. Impacts on humans

1.1. Health effects of hydro-fracking, production fluids and associated contaminants

The potential for hydro-fracking contaminants to be released to the atmosphere or groundwater in sufficient quantities to cause health effects in humans and wildlife.

1.2. Pollution caused by substance released during the exploration process is significant enough to cause a breach of environmental standards

1.3. Toxicity of contaminants

The potential for contaminants associated with and /or mobilised by hydraulic fracturing to cause harm to humans.

¹ An environmental risk assessment for shale gas exploratory operations in England - V.1, 2013

² Cuadrilla Risk Assessment Preston PNR_ERA, May 2014

1.4. Impacts from physical disruption

Physical disruption of the environment caused by hydraulic fracturing may have a detrimental impact on humans.

1.5. Impacts from ecological modification

Ecological modification caused by hydraulic fracturing may have a positive or negative impact on humans.

1.6. Water acquisition

Increased demand from surface waters, groundwater, river or the sea. May include use of potable supplied water and resource competition.

B. Impacts on flora and fauna

2.1 Effect of hydro-fracking, production fluids and associated contaminants on animals

Asphyxiation and/or other impacts on fauna could be endpoints relevant to performance and safety.

2.2 Effect of hydro-fracturing fluids on plants and algae

Elevated levels of hydro-fracking, production fluids and associated contaminants, in the soil, atmosphere and/or water may impact on the growth and/or calcification of plants and algae.

2.3 Ecotoxicology of contaminants

Should they migrate to the biosphere, contaminants associated with and/or mobilised by hydraulic fracturing may have a toxic effect on organisms.

2.4 Ecological effects

The degree of potential ecological disruption resulting from hydraulic fracturing may be an endpoint, especially if the ecosystem affected is considered valuable and/or sensitive to perturbations.

2.5 Modification of microbiological systems

The potential impact of hydraulic fracturing and its associated contaminants on aerobic and anaerobic microbial respiration in the geosphere, terrestrial and marine biosphere may be an endpoint. A low-pH, high CO₂ environment may favour some species and harm others, as would also be the case for methane.

C. Impacts on the physical environment

3.1 Contamination of groundwater

Contamination of groundwater resources may result in impacts on flora, fauna and/or humans if the water is abstracted or flows to the surface environment.

Contamination of groundwater can result from several sources, including: subsurface sources (note interconnection of layers during drilling); materials released during site preparation; the use of chemicals (delivery and mixing).

3.2 Impacts on soils and sediments

Increased hydro-fracking, production and / or contaminant fluid concentrations and/or contamination of soils and sediments with associated substances may be sufficient to modify the ecology and/or use of the impacted area by humans.

3.3 Management of flow back fluids leads to surface spills

3.4 Release to the atmosphere

Release of mobilised methane or other reservoir gases (e.g., radon, CO₂) to the atmosphere. The emitted gases to the atmosphere can contribute to the increase of the greenhouse gas effect, or lead to health impacts on humans and wildlife.

3.5 Impacts on exploitation of natural resources

Hydro-fracking can have an impact on the recovery of conventional hydrocarbons and other minerals.

3.6 Release to the marine environment

Release of hydro-fracking, production and / or contaminant fluids will alter the marine environment, leading to marine water acidification and potential negative impacts on marine flora and fauna.

3.7 Modified hydrology and hydrogeology

Changes in the deep hydrogeology or near-surface hydrology may affect aquifer flow or even surface hydrology for groundwater driven features. These impacts may be either positive or negative.

3.8 Modified geochemistry

The extent of geochemical modifications may be an endpoint of interest, due to resulting changes to geological processes. For example, the acidification of the geochemical regime may cause minerals to be dissolved, with potential implications for the porosity and stability of the geological formations.

3.9 Modified seismicity

Induced seismicity may be an endpoint of interest in itself, or it can result in other impacts, such as physical disruption of the surface environment that can result in sudden physical changes to the storage system.

3.10 Modified surface topography

Deformation of the terrestrial surface or sea-bed may be an endpoint of interest in itself, or may result in other impacts, such as damage to property.

3.11 Sinkhole formation

Large scale collapse structures may cause significant change to surface topography and possible hydro-fracking, production and / or contaminant fluid migration paths. Sinkholes can provide locations. .

3.12 Impacts on oceans

The potential impact on marine flora and fauna can be an assessment endpoint. Additionally, in case of CO₂ release it may cause acidification.

3.13 Subsidence or uplift

Drilling of wells, hydraulic fluid injection, hydraulic fracturing and subsequent production and abandonment may affect geological processes and may result in limited subsidence or uplift impacts of concern at the surface.

VII. Controls & mitigations

A. Schedule and planning

Relevant events may include phased drilling of wells and hydraulic fracturing, sealing of boreholes, and monitoring activities to provide data on the transient behaviour of the system or to provide input to the final assessment. The sequence of events and time between events may have implications for long term performance, e.g. chemical and hydraulic changes during a prolonged injection phase.

B. Pre-closure administrative control

The pre-closure administrative control will influence the quantity and quality of information about the hydraulic fracturing project that is available post-closure, therefore helping to determine societal memory. The better the amount and quality of information available, the lower the possibility of inadvertent intrusion.

C. Pre-closure monitoring of storage

Monitoring during the operational phase contributes towards the amount and quality of information initially available after closure concerning the behaviour of hydro-fracking, production and / or contaminant fluids and the distribution of hydro-fractured wells.

D. Post-fracking closure administrative control

There may be potential for loss of information in any transfer of administrative control. A lack of awareness about the details of a hydraulic fracturing project could result in inadvertent disruption in the future.

E. Post-fracking monitoring

Post-fracking monitoring may trigger post-closure remedial actions, if necessary.

F. Records and markers

It is expected that records will be kept to allow future generations to recall the existence and nature of the hydraulic fracturing following closure.

G. Reversibility

The degree to which reversibility is considered in the design of a hydraulic fracturing project may influence its long-term performance, such as by leaving viable boreholes in-situ after closure, for example.

H. Remedial actions

The aim of possible future remedial actions will be to modify the performance and safety of the hydraulic fractured system